

and magnetic susceptibility data are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1—M.P. ANALYSIS, CONDUCTANCE AND MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY DATA

Compound	M.P. °C	%metal		%Nitrogen		Λ_M $\text{Ohm}^{-1}\text{cm}^2$	μ_{eff} B.M.
		Found	Reqd	Found	Reqd		
[CuL]	174	12.15	12.46	5.34	5.49	8.0	1.78
[CuL']	158	11.07	11.89	4.86	5.02	8.5	1.75
[CdL]	197	19.82	20.13	4.89	5.01	9.0	—
[CdL']	184	18.29	18.53	4.37	4.61	10.5	—

LH₂ and L'H₂ = Schiff's bases derived from benzoin and ethylenediamine and *o*-phenylenediamine respectively.

Results and Discussion

Complexes reported in the present investigation have the composition [ML] and [ML'] where M = Cu(II), Cd(II) and LH₂ and L'H₂ are Schiff's bases derived from benzoin with ethylenediamine and *o*-phenylenediamine respectively. Copper complexes are green and cadmium complexes are white in colour. All the four complexes have low melting points and are fairly soluble in acetone, having low conductance values (Table 1) indicating non-electrolytic nature of the complexes.

The Schiff's bases can function as tetradentate ligands using two hydroxyl oxygens and two imino nitrogen atoms as the bonding sites. Assignments have been made for the two principal bands, i.e. $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ and $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ in the IR spectrum. In the ligands the appearance of a band at 1210 cm^{-1} due to $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ has shifted down to 1200 cm^{-1} in the complexes. The $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ band has appeared at 1600 and 1590 cm^{-1} which has shifted to lower frequency region for complexes [ML] and to higher frequency region for complexes of the type [ML']. However, conclusive evidence regarding the bonding of nitrogen and oxygen atoms have been provided by occurrence of $\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$ and $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$ around 515 and $\sim 440\text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively in the complexes⁵.

In the electronic spectra of Cu(II) complexes one broad band appears around 15000 region indicating a planar configuration for these complexes. Magnetic moment values of the Cu(II) complexes indicate the presence of one unpaired electron. From the analysis conductance and IR spectral studies of Cd(II) complexes are found to be four co-ordinated having a tetrahedral environment around the metal ions.

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Study of Camoquin-Ferrous Sulphate Complex

S. S. GUPTA, S. SIDDIQUI and R. KAUSHAL*

Chemical Laboratories, Motilal Vignyan Mahavidyalaya, Bhopal (M. P.)

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CAMOQUIN is more active than quinine against malaria. In continuation of our work¹⁻⁴ on the metal complexes of antimalarials, herein we describe camoquin-ferrous sulphate complex.

Experimental

Composition of the Complex :

(a) Standard solutions of ferrous sulphate (0.01 M) and camoquin base (0.005 M) were prepared in spectroscopically pure 80% methanol. 5 ml of the ligand was diluted to 200 ml and titrated against the metal solution using 'Toshniwal' conductivity bridge and dip type electrodes at 19° . The analysis of conductance data reveals that a 1 : 2 complex is formed in solution.

(b) The nature of the complex was studied spectrophotometrically on 'Spekol' using Vosburgh and Cooper⁵ Method. Mixtures containing 2 : 1, 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 proportions of equimolar solutions of ferrous sulphate and camoquin ($5 \times 10^{-4} M$) in spectroscopically pure methanol were taken. The plot of absorbance vs wavelength is given in Fig. 1.

(c) Formation of 1 : 2 complex was further confirmed by the following :

- (i) Job's Method⁶,
- (ii) Mole ratio Method⁷ and
- (iii) Slope ratio Method⁸.

Isolation and Analysis :

Camoquin base 1.0 g (1 M) was dissolved in methyl alcohol and ferrous sulphate 1.56 g (2 M) was dissolved in minimum quantity of methyl alcohol with two drops of sulphuric acid were mixed slowly to ferrous sulphate solution with constant stirring when a chocolate coloured complex was obtained immediately. It was cooled in an ice bath for four hours, filtered, washed with methyl alcohol and dried on porous plate ; yield 1.7 g. No attempt was made to prepare 1 : 1 complex.

* Retd. Scientist, Holkar Science College, INDORE (M.P.).

Found: Fe, 15.09; SO₄, 25.83; N, 5.28 and H₂O, 10.09; while C₂₀H₂₂ClN₃O.(FeSO₄)₂.4H₂O requires: Fe, 15.27; SO₄, 26.26; N, 5.74 and H₂O, 9.84.

Results and Discussion

The conductometric titration results clearly indicate that camoquin forms 1:1 and 1:2 complexes with ferrous sulphate; while Fig. 1 indicates that only one complex is formed. The spectrophotometric studies by (i) Job's method, (ii) Mole ratio method and (iii) Slope ratio method also indicate that the complexation takes place in the ratio 1:2. The analytical data agree with the composition C₂₀H₂₂ClN₃O.(FeSO₄)₂.4H₂O.

Fig. 1

The stability constants calculated by Job's and Yoe and Jones' method are 7.85 and 7.98 respectively. The free energy change ΔF has been calculated by the expression $\Delta F = -2.303 RT \log K$. The results are -10.81 and -11.06 K cal mole⁻¹ respectively.

The I.R. spectra of the ligand and complexes were recorded on Perkin-Elmer Model 237 spectrophotometer using KBr disc. Metal-nitrogen and

metal-oxygen absorption bands were observed at 655 and 680 cm⁻¹ respectively, while no such absorption bands were present in the ligand. Bonded sulphate shows strong absorption band at 1205 cm⁻¹. Band at 815 cm⁻¹ and 1655 cm⁻¹ indicate that co-ordinated water molecules are present in the complex. NH bending 1110 cm⁻¹, weak in parent compound becomes intense or modified to 1120 cm⁻¹ on complexation indicating metal-NH co-ordination. C-N stretching vibrations of aromatic secondary amine is modified from 1260 to 1270 cm⁻¹ on complexation; while C=N stretching vibration of ligand is modified from 1630 (weak) to 1640 (strong) on complexation. NH stretching of secondary aryl amine increases on complex formation from 3230 to 3340 cm⁻¹.

It may be mentioned that I. R. spectra of the complex show characteristic absorption bands of phenolic OH group namely 1010, 1205 and 1355 cm⁻¹. No unambiguous conclusion is possible regarding the structure of the complex.

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Studies on Complexes of Metal(II) Carboxylates with Donor Molecules: Part I. Complexes of Copper(II) Alkanoates with Aromatic Amine N-oxides and Triphenylphosphine Oxide

N. KUMAR, P. L. KACHROO and R. KANT

Department of Chemistry, University of Jammu, Jammu-180 001, India

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COPPER(II) carboxylates and their complexes with nitrogen donors have been intensively investigated because of their interesting structures and anti-ferromagnetic properties^{1,2}. However, there is no